

**CONSERVATION OF PRIORITY SPECIES OF MARINE MEGAFUNA
IN GREECE AND ITALY**

D6.1: Extract of the project data from the LIFE KPI webtool

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LIFE22-NAT-EL-LIFE MareNatura

“Conservation of priority species of marine megafauna in Greece and Italy”

**Grant Agreement Project 101113792 –
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Abbreviations

KPIs	Key Project Indicators
FTE	Full-time employees

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Summary

The deliverable D6.1 – Extract of the project data from the LIFE KPI webtool provides an initial snapshot of the LIFE MareNatura Project KPIs. These KPIs were decided during the first months of the project, and they will be monitored throughout the duration of LIFE MareNatura project. The indicator context selection is described in Chapter 1, followed by the selected indicators in Chapter 2 and indicator values in Chapter 3.

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Chapter 1. Indicator Context

Overarching context

Different sub-contexts have been selected for the LIFE MareNatura project corresponding to the Biogeographic region and the territorial extent of the project as well as the Natura 2000 sites included in the project area.

C.1.1 Biogeographic regions: Mediterranean, Marine Mediterranean

C.1.2. Territorial extent: EL – Ελλάδα & IT – Italia

C.1.4. Natura 2000 sites: 41 Greek Natura 2000 sites are in Greece, and 3 are in Italy (Table 1).

Table 1. Natura 2000 sites included in the LIFE MareNatura project.

Code	Name
GR1110013	Thalassia Periochi Thrakis
GR1150014	Thalassia Periochi Kavalas - Thasou
GR1430004	Ethniko Thalassio Parko Alonnisou – Voreion Sporadon, Anatoliki Skopelos
GR1430005	Nisia Kyra Panagia, Piperi, Psathoura Kai Gyro Nisides Agios Georgios, Nisoi Adelfoi, Lechousa, Gaidouronisia
GR2110001	Amvrakikos Kolpos, Delta Lourou Kai Arachthou (Petra, Mytikas, Evryteri Periochi, Kato Pous Arachthou, Kampi Filippiadas)
GR2210002	Kolpos Lagana Zakynthou (Akr. Geraki - Keri) Kai Nisides Marathonisi Kai Pelouzo
GR2210004	Nisides Stamfani Kai Arpyia (Strofades), Kai Thalassia Zoni
GR2220003	Esoteriko Archipelagos Ioniou (Meganisi, Arkoudi, Atokos, Vromonas)
GR2220007	Thalassia Zoni Apo Argostoli Eos Ormo Mounta
GR2230004	Nisoi Paxoi Kai Antipaxoi Kai Evryteri Thalassia Periochi
GR2230008	Diapontia Nisia (Othonoi, Ereikousa, Mathraki Kai Vrachonisides),
GR2310001	Delta Achelou, Limnothalassa Mesolongiou - Aitolikou, Ekvoles Evinou, Nisoi Echinades, Nisos Petalas
GR2330005	Thines Kai Paraliako Dasos Zacharos, Limni Kaiafa, Strofylia, Kakovatos
GR2330008	Thalassia Periochi Kolpou Kyparissias: Akr. Katakolo - Kyparissia
GR2420009	Nisides Skyrou Kai Thalassia Periochi
GR2420016	Thalassia Periochi Notiou Evvoikou Kolpou
GR2530007	Korinthiakos Kolpos
GR2540002	Periochi Neapolis Kai Nisos Elafonisos
GR2540003	Ekvoles Evrota, Periochi Vrontama Kai Thalassia Periochi Lakonikou Kolpou
GR2550005	Thines Kyparissias (Neochori - Kyparissia)
GR2550010	Thalassia Periochi Notias Messinias
GR3000012	Nisos Antikythira Kai Nisides Prasonisi, Lagouvardos, Plakoulithra Kai Nisides Thymonies
GR3000019	Thalassia Periochi Kythiron
GR4210001	Kasos kai Kasonisia – Evryteri Thalassia Periochi
GR4210003	Voreia Karpathos Kai Saria Kai Paraktia Thalassia Zoni
GR4210011	Vrachonisia Notiou Aigaiou: Velopoula, Falkonera, Ananes, Christiana, Pacheia, Fteno, Makra, Astakidonisia, Syrna - Gyro Nisia Kai Thalassia

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	Zoni
GR4210021	Anatoliko Tmima Astypaleas Kai Nisides Kounoupi, Fteno, Chondropoulo, Koitsomytis, Moni, Agia Kyriaki, Tigani, Chondri, Ligno, Fokionisia, Katsagrelis, Pontikoysa, Fidoysa, Ktenia Kai Thalassia Periochi
GR4210023	Nisides Karpathiou Pelagous: Megalo Sofrano, Sochas, Mikro Sofrano, Avgo, Divounia, Chamili, Astakidonia
GR4210025	Anatoliko Tmima Nisou Symis Kai Nisides Kouloundros Seskli, Troumpeto, Marmaras, Karavalonisi, Megalonisi, Gialesino, Oxeia, Chondros, Platy, Nimos Kai Thalassia Periochi Nisou Symis
GR4210028	Nisos Kasos Kai Symplegma Kasonision Kai Thalassia Periochi
GR4220006	Nisos Polyaigos - Kimolos
GR4220021	Mikres Kyklades, Voreioanatoliki Amorgos, Anatolikes Aktes Donousas, Gyro Nisides Kai Thalassia Periochi
GR4220027	Nisides Mykonou: Rineia, Chtapodia, Kai Tragonisi Kai Thalassia Periochi
GR4220033	Nisos Gyaros Kai Thalassia Zoni
GR4310004	Dytika Asterousa (Apo Agiofarango Eos Kokkino Pyrgo),
GR4320006	Voreioanatoliko Akro Kritis: Dionysades, Elasa Kai Chersonisos Sidero (Akra Mavro Mouri – Vai – Akra Plakas) Kai Thalassia Zoni
GR4320011	Dionysades Nisoi Kai Thalassia Zoni
GR4330004	Prassano Farangi - Patsos - Sfakoryako Rema - Paralia Rethymnou Kai Ekvoli Geropotamou, Akr. Lianos Kavos - Perivolia
GR4340003	Chersonisos Rodopou – Paralia Maleme – Kolpos Chanion
GR4340013	Nisoi Gavdos Kai Gavdopoula
GR4340024	Thalassia Periochi Dytikis Kai Notiodytikis Kritis
IT9110040	Isole Tremiti
IT9120012	Scoglio dell' Eremita
IT9150015	Litorale di Gallipoli e Isola S. Andrea

Specific context

Five specific contexts were developed to better describe and align with the selected indicators. Three of these contexts relate to indicators monitoring the pilot conservation actions. More details are found in Table 2.

Table 2. Selected Specific contexts

Specific context name	Overarching contexts
Rat eradication	GR2210004 (SPA)
Length of shore managed	GR2550005 (SCI/SAC)
All Natura 2000 sites and territories	Mediterranean Marine Mediterranean, EL, IT, GR4210003 (SPA and SCI/SAC), GR4220033 (SPA and SCI/SAC), IT9110040 (SPA), GR2210004 (SPA), GR1430005 (SPA), GR2230008 (SPA), GR2420009 (SPA), GR3000012 (SPA), GR4210021 (SPA), GR4210023 (SPA), GR4210025 (SPA), GR4210028 (SPA), GR4220021 (SPA), GR4220027 (SPA), GR4320011 (SPA), IT9150015 (SPA and SCI/SAC), GR4220006 (SCI/SAC), GR4310004 (SCI/SAC), GR4320006 (SCI/SAC),

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	GR4330004 (SCI/SAC), GR4340003 (SCI/SAC), GR4340013 (SCI/SAC), GR1430004 (SPA and SCI/SAC), GR2110001 (SCI/SAC), GR2210002 (SCI/SAC), GR2220003 (SCI/SAC), GR2230004 (SCI/SAC), GR2310001 (SCI/SAC), GR2330005 (SCI/SAC), GR2330008 (SCI/SAC), GR2540002 (SCI/SAC), GR2540003 (SCI/SAC), GR4210001 (SCI/SAC), GR4210011 (SCI/SAC), GR1110013 (SCI/SAC), GR1150014 (SPA and SCI/SAC), GR2220007 (SCI/SAC), GR2420016 (SPA), GR2530007 (SCI/SAC), GR2550010 (SCI/SAC), GR3000019 (SPA), GR4340024 (SCI/SAC), IT9120012 (SPA), GR2550005 (SCI/SAC)
<i>Caretta caretta</i> N2K sites and territories	EL GR1110013 (SCI/SAC), GR1430004 (SPA and SCI/SAC), GR2110001 (SCI/SAC), GR2210002 (SCI/SAC), GR2220003 (SCI/SAC), GR2220007 (SCI/SAC), GR2230004 (SCI/SAC), GR2310001 (SCI/SAC), GR2330005 (SCI/SAC), GR2330008 (SCI/SAC), GR2550005 (SCI/SAC), GR2530007 (SCI/SAC), GR2540002 (SCI/SAC), GR2540003 (SCI/SAC), GR2550010 (SCI/SAC), GR4210001 (SCI/SAC), GR4210003 (SPA and SCI/SAC), GR4220006 (SCI/SAC), GR4310004 (SCI/SAC), GR4330004 (SCI/SAC), GR4340003 (SCI/SAC), GR4340013 (SCI/SAC), GR4340024 (SCI/SAC)
Monk seal cave restoration	GR1430004 (SPA and SCI/SAC)

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Chapter 2. Project-Specific Settings and Indicator Selection

14 indicators were selected belonging to 8 KPI categories (Table 3). The selected indicators are measuring:

- D. Project setting, area/length and population
- E. Environmental and Climate action outputs and outcomes
- F. Societal outputs and outcomes
- G. Economic outputs and outcomes

Table 3. Selected indicators

Code	Category name	Indicator code & name
1.5.B.		1.5.B - Project work area
1.6.B.		1.6.B - Humans impacted by the project
7.B.	Nature and Biodiversity	7.2.B - Natural and semi-natural habitats
		7.3.B - Wildlife species
10.B	Governance	10.1.2.B - Number of supervisory/enforcement bodies engaged by the project
		10.1.3.B - Achievements by project in compliance, enforcement or legislation
		10.3.B - Professional training, capacity building and education
11.B.	Information and awareness	11.1.B - Website
		11.2.B - Other tools for reaching/raising awareness
12.B.	Network and synergies	12.1.B - Networking and synergies with projects/initiatives
13.B		13.B - New jobs created
14.B.	Economic sustainability and Catalytic effect	14.1.B - Revenue during or after project end, due to project outcomes
		14.2.B - Catalytic effect - Financial - Cumulative investments triggered or finance accessed
		14.3.B - Continuation after the project-end in the same premises/area (s), as those used during the project

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Chapter 3. Indicator Values

1.5.B - Project work area

This indicator relates to the total area of marine space surveyed. It refers to the extent of the ecological surveys (boat and aerial survey transects, radar surveys, biological sample collection) that will be carried out. Within this area, telemetry schemes will also be applied to the target species and sentinel species.

Specific context: All Natura 2000 sites and territories

Descriptor: Area of monitoring activities to assess the outcomes/impacts of project environmental/climate actions (e.g. through sensors, surveys, visits, etc).

Begin value	End Value	Beyond 5 Years Value	Unit
0	48,000,000.00	48,000,000.00	ha

1.6.B - Humans impacted by the project

Number of site managers and decision makers trained. At least 100 site managers and decision-makers are expected to be trained throughout the project through the Marine Conservation School and other relevant project activities. NECCA will continue to train site managers after the end of the project, therefore it is estimated that 50 more people will be trained within 5 years after project completion.

Participants' lists of every training session will be submitted with the final report and used as evidence for this indicator.

Specific context: All Natura 2000 sites and territories

First level descriptor: Type of impact – Persons with improved capacity or knowledge due to project actions

Second level descriptor: Type of persons – Non-resident persons regularly present within or near the project area (e.g. employees, students)

Begin value	End Value	Beyond 5 Years Value	Unit
0	100	150	Number of persons impacted

7.2.B - Natural and semi-natural habitats

1. Related conservation action – Rat eradication

It is estimated that rat eradication will occur at 140ha of the breeding habitat of Scopoli's shearwater. The eradication of pests is expected to decrease the breeding failure of Scopoli's shearwater. The breeding success of the colony is going to be measured before and after the completion of the activity. The results of the monitoring will be submitted with the Final Report.

The appointed habitat type is indicative since the terrestrial part of the SPA consists of phrygana Sarcopoterium spinosum, arborescent matorrals with Juniperus spp., vegetated sea cliffs of the Mediterranean coasts with endemic Limonium spp. and artificial landscapes (26% of the area's surface).

Specific context: Rat eradication

First level descriptor: Annex I Habitats Directive

Second level descriptor: 1240-Vegetated sea cliffs of the Mediterranean coasts with endemic Limonium spp.

a. Area/Length of habitat where loss of biodiversity is being halted and reversed due to your project (due to existing habitat restored and/or newly created/developed habitat)

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Begin value	End Value	Beyond 5 Years Value	Unit
0.00	140.00	140.00	ha

b. Part of the Area/Length of habitat indicated in line "a" which is newly created/developed habitat (ex-novo)

Begin value	End Value	Beyond 5 Years Value	Unit
0.00	0.00	0.00	ha

c. Part of the Area/Length of habitat (existing habitat restored or newly created/developed) indicated in line "a" which is within a Nat2K Site

Begin value	End Value	Beyond 5 Years Value	Unit
0.00	140.00	140.00	ha

2. Related conservation action for sea turtles – Length of shore managed

Conservation actions will be implemented at the core nesting site of *Caretta caretta* species in Southern Kyparissia Bay. The number of nests (indicating the increase in nesting effort) will be monitored before, during, and after the completion of the action. The results of the monitoring will be submitted with the Final Report. Nonetheless, due to the species' life cycle, the actual effects and results of this activity will be truly measurable 15 years after the project is completed.

The area of interest has sand-dune ecosystems which are in well-developed formations, i.e., a strip of sand, followed by low sand-dunes, and high dunes, with ammophilous vegetation, then high dunes with *Pinus halepensis* forests. The appointed habitat type is indicative.

Specific context: Length of shore managed

First level descriptor: Annex I Habitats Directive

Second level descriptor: 2110-Embryonic shifting dunes

a. Area/Length of habitat where loss of biodiversity is being halted and reversed due to your project (due to existing habitat restored and/or newly created/developed habitat)

Begin value	End Value	Beyond 5 Years Value	Unit
0.00	9.5	9.5	km

b. Part of the Area/Length of habitat indicated in line "a" which is newly created/developed habitat (ex-novo)

Begin value	End Value	Beyond 5 Years Value	Unit
0.00	0.00	0.00	km

c. Part of the Area/Length of habitat (existing habitat restored or newly created/developed) indicated in line "a" which is within a Nat2K Site

Begin value	End Value	Beyond 5 Years Value	Unit
0.00	9.5	9.5	km

3. Related conservation action – restoration of monk seal pupping sites

Restoration of 3 *Monachus monachus* pupping sites. The area will be specified after selecting the caves.

Specific context: Length of shore managed

First level descriptor: Annex I Habitats Directive

Second level descriptor: 8330-Submerged or partially submerged sea caves

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a. Area/Length of habitat where loss of biodiversity is being halted and reversed due to your project (due to existing habitat restored and/or newly created/developed habitat)

Begin value	End Value	Beyond 5 Years Value	Unit

b. Part of the Area/Length of habitat indicated in line "a" which is newly created/developed habitat (ex-novo)

Begin value	End Value	Beyond 5 Years Value	Unit

c. Part of the Area/Length of habitat (existing habitat restored or newly created/developed) indicated in line "a" which is within a Nat2K Site

Begin value	End Value	Beyond 5 Years Value	Unit

*** Values will be provided later**

7.3.B - Wildlife species

1. Related conservation action – Rat eradication

The values will be defined at a later stage (monitoring undergoing) which will have to be combined with the terrestrial extent (number of islands) that the rat eradication will take place. The project monitoring plan is under development - methods to assess the actual impact of the pilot conservation actions on this sentinel species.

Most appropriate flag would be 'pest eradication'.

Specific context: Rat eradication

First level descriptor: EU Birds Directive Annex I

Second level descriptor: *Calonectris diomedea*/Birds

Species Range Area			
Begin value	End Value	Beyond 5 Years Value	Unit

Population count method for Birds			
Begin value	End Value	Beyond 5 Years Value	Unit

Total species population count in the Member States included in the context			
Begin value	End Value	Beyond 5 Years Value	Unit

*** Values will be provided later**

2. Related conservation action for sea turtles – Length of shore managed

The project monitoring plan is under development - methods to assess the actual impact of the pilot conservation actions on the target species.

Specific context: Length of shore managed

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First level descriptor: EU Habitats Directive Annex IV

Second level descriptor: *Caretta caretta*/Reptiles

Species Range Area			
Begin value	End Value	Beyond 5 Years Value	Unit

Population count method for Birds			
Begin value	End Value	Beyond 5 Years Value	Unit

Total species population count in the Member States included in the context			
Begin value	End Value	Beyond 5 Years Value	Unit

*** Values will be provided later**

3. Related conservation action for sea turtles – restoration of monk seal pupping sites

The project monitoring plan is under development - methods to assess the actual impact of the pilot conservation actions on the target species.

Specific context: Monk seal cave restoration

First level descriptor: EU Habitats Directive Annex IV

Second level descriptor: *Monachus monachus*/Mammals

Species Range Area			
Begin value	End Value	Beyond 5 Years Value	Unit

Population count method for Birds			
Begin value	End Value	Beyond 5 Years Value	Unit

Total species population count in the Member States included in the context			
Begin value	End Value	Beyond 5 Years Value	Unit

*** Values will be provided later**

10.1.2.B - Number of supervisory/enforcement bodies engaged by the project

New marine protected areas will be designated by the end or soon after the project's completion - duty holder engagement at the Ministry level is necessary for its completion. The project will also provide means for public authorities to monitor and manage the new MPA through the marine conservation school. Additionally, by the end of the project, an early warning system and an integrated monitoring plan will have been developed. The latter will also incorporate 150 Site-Specific conservation objectives. Marine managers and decision makers will be trained on the Systematic Conservation Planning framework developed by LIFE MareNatura Outcomes. The public entity coordinating all Managing bodies in Greece is part of the LIFE MareNatura consortium and by the end of the project, we expect at least one more public entity to engage in the project activities.

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Specific context: All Natura 2000 sites and territories

First level descriptor: National authorities

Begin value	End Value	Beyond 5 Years Value	Unit
1	2	2	Number of supervisory / enforcement bodies involved

10.1.3.B - Achievements by project in compliance, enforcement or legislation

1. Achievement I

Responds to consultations will be measured based on the comments submitted at every consultation.

Specific context: All Natura 2000 sites and territories

First level descriptor: Policy feedback actions (e.g. responding to consultations, inputs to policy makers)

Begin value	End Value	Beyond 5 Years Value	Unit

** Values will be provided later*

2. Achievement II

20 new marine Natura 2000 sites will be designated before or shortly after the end of the project, based on the Mediterranean Biodiversity Inventory of hot-spots. Nonetheless, those areas might be merged into larger areas depending on the data produced by the project. Measure: publication in Government Gazette.

Specific context: All Natura 2000 sites and territories

First level descriptor: New or adapted legislation/strategies/plans

Begin value	End Value	Beyond 5 Years Value	Unit
0	20	20	Number of achievements

10.3.B - Professional training, capacity building and education

1. Public body employees

Capacity building and training of NECCA personnel through participation in project thematic workshops, training sessions, and through the Marine Conservation School and training of marine managers on systematic conservation principles. The values as defined in the Grant Agreement. Participants' lists of every training session will be submitted with the final report and used as evidence for this indicator.

Specific context: All Natura 2000 sites and territories

First level descriptor: Professional training/Capacity building

Second level descriptor: Public body employees

Begin value	End Value	Beyond 5 Years Value	Unit
0	100	150	No. of individuals

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2. Volunteers trained

Training of volunteers on inspecting *Caretta caretta* nesting sites.

Specific context: *Caretta caretta* N2K sites and territories

First level descriptor: Professional training/Capacity building

Second level descriptor: Volunteers trained

Begin value	End Value	Beyond 5 Years Value	Unit

** Values will be provided later*

11.1.B – Website

Measured via Google Analytics.

Specific context: All Natura 2000 sites and territories

First level descriptor: No. of unique visits

Begin value	End Value	Beyond 5 Years Value	Unit
0.00	42000	44000	Number of unique website visits

11.2.B - Other tools for reaching/raising awareness

1. Number of articles in print media (e.g. newspaper and magazine articles)

Measured by number of articles published.

Specific context: All Natura 2000 sites and territories

Descriptor: Number of articles in print media (e.g. newspaper and magazine articles)

Begin value	End Value	Beyond 5 Years Value	Unit
0	2	3	Number of outcomes (e.g. nr of reports, events, etc)

2. Number of different publications made (Journal/conference)

Measured by articles published in scientific journals, conference proceedings, and conference book of abstracts.

Specific context: All Natura 2000 sites and territories

Descriptor: Number of different publications made (Journal/conference).

Begin value	End Value	Beyond 5 Years Value	Unit
0	9	11	Number of outcomes (e.g. nr of reports, events, etc)

3. Number of events/exhibitions organised

As per Grant Agreement: Photo exhibition of 10 sets of 14 to 28 photos (printed and digital) will be displayed at communication events, local festivals, or local events. After project completion, 8 of those sets will be displayed on the facilities of 7 beneficiaries (e.g. HCMR - CretAquarium, UoC - NHMC Exhibition Hall, NECCA etc.).

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Specific context: All Natura 2000 sites and territories

Descriptor: Number of events/exhibitions organized

Begin value	End Value	Beyond 5 Years Value	Unit
0	33	41	Number of outcomes (e.g. nr of reports, events, etc)

4. Other distinct media products created (e.g. different videos/broadcast/leaflets)

2 videos (a project promo video and a documentary), 1 leaflet, 1 school kit, and 1 Guide book will be produced.

Specific context: All Natura 2000 sites and territories

Descriptor: Other distinct media products created (e.g. different videos/broadcast/leaflets)

Begin value	End Value	Beyond 5 Years Value	Unit
0	5	5	Number of outcomes (e.g. nr of reports, events, etc)

12.1.B - Networking and synergies with projects/initiatives

1. Other EU-funded projects

Interreg projects.

Specific context: All Natura 2000 sites and territories

Descriptor: Other EU-funded projects

Begin value	End Value	Beyond 5 Years Value	Unit
0	2	2	No. of projects/initiatives

2. LIFE projects

Values were calculated based on the number of projects that we expect to network with and exchange knowledge.

Specific context: All Natura 2000 sites and territories

Descriptor: LIFE projects

Begin value	End Value	Beyond 5 Years Value	Unit
0	4	4	No. of projects/initiatives

3. Other projects or initiatives (nationally/regionally/privately funded)

Researchers will meet in person in the field.

Measure: number of signed Memorandum of Understanding

Specific context: All Natura 2000 sites and territories

Descriptor: Other projects or initiatives (nationally/regionally/privately funded; to be specified in the comments box...)

Begin value	End Value	Beyond 5 Years Value	Unit
0	1	1	No. of projects/initiatives

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13.B - New jobs created

The values were calculated by subtracting the budget of the own contribution financing (this matches the current personnel) from the total personnel cost. Continuously, the no of FTE was calculated based on the different average monthly rates of each beneficiary. The No. of FTE values concerns the whole duration of the project (72 months). New jobs created in the Management Units of NECCA will be maintained beyond 5 years of project end.

We speculate that by the end of the project, the number of FTE will be higher than the one stated here due to third-party co-financing. These values will be updated as the project progresses.

The values stated refer to new jobs being created, according to our project's budget.

Specific context: All Natura 2000 sites and territories

Descriptor: New jobs created within the project consortium

Begin value	End Value	Beyond 5 Years Value	Unit
0.00	14.33	5.80	No. of FTE

14.1.B - Revenue during or after project end, due to project outcomes

This project will not have any revenue from sales/fees of goods or services. Deliverables and results will be open to the public.

Specific context: All Natura 2000 sites and territories

Descriptor: Revenue from a mix of sources or from other sources (please clarify in comment)

Begin value	End Value	Beyond 5 Years Value	Unit
0.00	0.00	0.00	€

14.2.B - Catalytic effect - Financial - Cumulative investments triggered or finance accessed

The designation of new MPAs is expected to result in research grants following project completion. The KPIs could not be submitted without inserting values on 14.2.B. The values above need revision.

Specific context: All Natura 2000 sites and territories

Descriptor: Grants, subsidies

Begin value	End Value	Beyond 5 Years Value	Unit
0.00	0.00	20,000.00	€

14.3.1.B - Continuation after the project-end in the same premises/area (s), as those used during the project

It is expected that some activities such as the Marine Conservation School and Marine Conservation Task Force, will continue after the project end.

Specific context: All Natura 2000 sites and territories

Descriptor: Continuation at lower scale (compared to the scale during project implementation).

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